

THE INCREASING NECESSITY OF SKILLS DIVERSITY IN TEAM TEACHING

TS Craig¹

Department of Applied Mathematics, University of Twente
Enschede, The Netherlands
ORCID 0000-0002-3653-2995

S Redeker

Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Twente
Enschede, The Netherlands
ORCID 0000-0003-3240-1792

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ABSTRACT

The advantages of including technological tools, for example dynamic graphing software, into the teaching and learning of technical subjects have long been recognised. Using such tools effectively in the classroom is at least partially constrained by the teacher's knowledge and skills. Any teaching team benefits from skills diversity and always has, however, in recent years the skills needed for effective use of the tools available are becoming more numerous and more varied. Using a range of tools for assessment, rather than for in-class teaching and learning, demands an extra burden of care. Using an example from our own recent experience we illustrate the need for skills diversity in teams teaching and raise questions related to traditional assessment in mathematics.

1 INTRODUCTION

The value of technological tools for the learning and teaching of mathematics has long been recognised, from early computer algebra systems to today's powerful visualisation and computational packages. Over the past two decades such tools have gone from fringe elements of the classroom to being core features. GeoGebra, for example, is an excellent package to use in vector calculus as it requires no coding experience on the part of students or teacher and contributes valuable 3-dimensional visualisation. In specifically engineering contexts another example is LTspice simulating software, which lets the user model the behaviour of simple and

¹ *Corresponding Author*

TS Craig

t.s.craig@utwente.nl

complex (analog) circuits. Programming languages specific to engineering, such as MATLAB, are also widely used.

Many examples can be found in practice and in the academic literature on using these tools in the classroom for active teaching and learning purposes, yet far fewer examples can be found of them being used in assessment. Mathematics exams continue overwhelmingly to be closed book, written individually in a secure environment, without access to electronic devices. The reasons for not including digital tools in an exam are many and varied. For example, do we wish to assess whether our students can solve integrals by hand, or visualise and draw surfaces and curves without technological help? Additionally, tools that require access to the internet have inherent security concerns.

So why did we choose to carry out a technology mediated exam? The pandemic experience, forcing us to shift into uncomfortable spaces and to accept hitherto unacceptable options, also forced us to look at how we assessed in a new light. In the case of vector calculus we came to recognise that access to graphing software, powerful calculators and many reference materials could be seen as a boon.

This short paper forms part of documenting a larger project of exploring the design journey of shifting from traditional assessment to technology-mediated assessment in vector calculus. Elsewhere [1,2,7] we have discussed design principles, consequences for pedagogy and comparison of student results. This paper contributes to the conversation on team teaching in mathematics, highlighting the need for explicit roles to be filled by the team members. We provide context of the technology-mediated assessment project, discuss certain aspects of team teaching with special emphasis on roles, then analyse our practice in terms of roles and team teaching practice.

2 CONTEXT

Our vector calculus course runs February-April. In March/April 2020 and again in 2021 we were forced to have our vector calculus exams written remotely, at home, necessarily open book. Despite the challenges we experienced we recognised the value of allowing students to use the many powerful tools available to them. We were forced into a position of setting questions that assessed for higher order skills and conceptual understanding instead of falling back on questions that were more procedural or relied on memory. We have written about this elsewhere [1,2].

There are distinct disadvantages to the mode we were forced to accept in 2020 and 2021, primarily security. Now, in 2022, we are returning to writing the exams under secure circumstances but aim to retain the best aspects of the previous two years. Before the pandemic students wrote the exam without a calculator or notes. Now we allow a formula sheet, a graphical calculator and use of a Chromebook virtual environment including access to GeoGebra, Symbolab and course slides. GeoGebra is 2d and 3d graphing software and Symbolab is a powerful online calculator.

3 TEAM TEACHING

3.1 Team teaching roles and phases

[3] observe that the complexities of higher education are increasingly making team teaching a necessity rather than a choice. For example blended learning (in which learning activities are a blend of online and face to face) requires a teaching team with a variety of roles and skills [4] and interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary programmes require teachers to work in teams [5] to “collaboratively design courses that allow for the integration of various disciplines” [5: p. 198].

Clear roles for the members of the team are important [4,5]. [4] warn that failing to clarify roles incurs a “risk of assuming a perceived understanding around expectations” [4: p. 869] which can impact teaching practices. The role of leader within the team is of particular importance [4,5] although that role can rotate within the team [6]. Members of the team assume roles appropriate to their knowledge and skills and to the needs of the pedagogic environment. Beyond the roles of the teaching team, [4] observe that the students themselves adopt roles, such as active contributor, observer and evolving expert.

[5] outline three phases of collaborative course design, which are “preparation (phase 1: planning), teaching (phase 2: enactment) and evaluation (phase 3: reflection).” (p. 198) They advise that in phase 1 pedagogic needs must be prioritised over practical decisions and in phase 2 adaptation to the needs of the students must be possible. Our short paper contributes to the reflection phase of our design project.

3.2 Our team roles and practice

Our team was made up of the first author, a co-teacher and a member of the university’s e-assessment group. The first author assumed the leadership role. She was responsible for setting the exam, facilitating communication within the team and ensuring that the students were well informed about the assessment with opportunity to practise the skills required. The second member of the team co-taught on the course and advised on exam design. The third member of the team was an e-assessment specialist. He managed the Chromebook environment and liaised with the technical team and exam venue management.

Our team teaching practice [4] began a year before the exam with the formation of the team, planning, and booking use of the university Chromebooks. During the enactment phase the two teachers on the team incorporated use of the digital tools into the teaching and learning resources. They designed the exam questions, aiming for assessment of conceptual understanding and higher order thinking skills, and “stress tested” them using the digital tools. On several occasions the whole team met to consider the design of the virtual environment. The first author and the e-assessment specialist communicated with technical staff and venue management.

The three key activities were exam design, technical set up and communication. These three activities were performed competently, thoughtfully and timeously. Nothing should have gone wrong and yet something almost did.

3.3 A flaw in the system

The second author was a student taking the vector calculus course. Through active engagement with the digital tools he took on the impromptu role of evolving expert [4] and became aware of characteristics of the tools which had implications for the security aspect of the exam. He familiarised himself with the full extent of the weaknesses in the system and devised a plan for closing the security holes. He informed the first author of the situation and thereafter the virtual environment was redesigned to make it more secure.

Both Symbolab and Geogebra allow users to work remotely in groups with one another, which would jeopardise the security of the exam. GeoGebra furthermore has the option of uploading documents into one's profile, thereby creating inequitable open book environments. We must be clear about calling certain features of the tools we had chosen to use "weaknesses". These are not weaknesses of the packages overall, they are rather an impediment to secure, individually-written exams.

The exam proceeded without a hitch. After the exam the second author remained in the exam venue, testing the security of the virtual environment in a variety of ways.

We are now in phase 3 (reflection) of the design process, which includes reflecting on what went wrong and how we could have avoided it. We are reminded of [4]'s warning that roles should be clarified to avoid perceived expectations. The teachers implicitly assumed all technical considerations to be in the purview of the e-assessment specialist, yet he (quite accurately) did not consider testing for security flaws in the digital tools to be part of his mandate. The exam itself was "stress tested" for use in the planned virtual environment, yet the environment itself was merely approved for looking as the team expected it to look; it was not stress tested for flaws or weaknesses.

In hindsight we recognise that what was missing from the team was someone with the role of stress testing the virtual environment, having both the technical skills to do so and close familiarity with the digital tools themselves. How this gap in the team might have been avoided would have been to explicitly identify the roles needing to be filled and to ensure that the team could fill those roles. A scenario planning brainstorming session early in the project would have been valuable.

4 CONCLUSION

Many higher education environments require the skills of more than simply one lecturer with a whiteboard, such as blended learning [4], interdisciplinary modules [5] and technology mediated assessment. Team teaching (or team working) [3] is called for in such cases. With the ubiquity of digital teaching and learning resources and tools, the recent increase in remote learning and a diverse student body, all embedded in a world facing local and global challenges, we suggest that not only is team teaching of vital importance, but the team should be carefully constructed to embody the diversity of skills required.

We have found the framing of “roles” useful for analysing our practice and how it (almost) failed. We suggest that, upon embarking on a team taught project, an explicit effort is made to identify all necessary roles and to ensure the needs of those roles can be met by the team. This could perhaps be achieved by a scenario-planning brainstorming session. Everyone on the team needs to be aware of their roles to avoid perceived understanding of expectations.

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Better informed on how to proceed with team teaching we are left with some fundamental questions. Should we even be shifting towards technology-mediated assessment given inherent security concerns? Should we only use software designed for assessment purposes in that case? Should we be assessing “securely” at all, that is, should we rather assess mathematical proficiency using groupwork or take home assignments? These are all questions informing our work as we aim to problematize and improve assessment in vector calculus.

In closing we observe that our contribution answers the call of [4] to include students as co-authors and co-researchers in the scholarship of teaching and learning. We gratefully acknowledge Tugce Akkaya and Amanuel Gecer for their invaluable contributions to this project. For further information on this project, including comparison of results, we direct the reader to [1], [2] and [7].

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